

Design Challenges on Machine-Learning enabled Resource Optimization

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Abstract— Nowadays, Service Providers’ (SPs) need for efficient resource utilization solutions is more demanding than ever. The optimal use of the physical and virtual infrastructures guarantees on one hand that the provided services are going to meet the required Quality of Service (QoS) levels, and on the other that the waste of resources due to overdesign is minimized. However, the prediction of the exact amount of the required resources per service at any time of its lifecycle is not an easy process. For this purpose, we propose a solution which handles the infrastructure in a holistic manner introducing a novel architecture and its open-source implementation that exploits the monitoring data from three layers (hardware, virtualization and application) and uses them to train machine learning models, which can accurately predict the exact number of the required resources per Service Level Agreement (SLA) contract.

Index Terms— machine learning, next generation networking, software defined networking.

I. INTRODUCTION

TRADITIONALLY, the challenge for any given network infrastructure is to maximize the number of the supported user services while respecting the desired QoS. The interplay between the processing, storage and network resources devoted to a service and the QoS it experiences has been the focus of studies from the very beginning of telecommunication systems. At the same time, continuous efforts towards more dynamic, intelligent, and sophisticated network management solutions have resulted in new concepts, like the Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies which are currently at their hype [1], offering high configuration flexibility to network operators. In this dynamic environment, network operators struggle to maximize the benefits from their infrastructures [2], [3]. So, they need mechanisms that can predict the necessary resources for each running service per level of QoS. This requires knowledge of the profile of each service, which is on its own another challenge, as new types of services emerge every day. This creates a dynamic and extremely complex environment from the resource allocation perspective, while the continuously increasing communication speeds imply decision making in shorter intervals and at a finer level. Another key point that deserves attention is the heterogeneity of the infrastructure used in the modern datacenters. Hardware equipment (i.e., physical servers, switches, routers, etc.) in combination with several virtualization technologies are used to provide virtual network and computational resources. This mandates the monitoring and management of the allocated resources on physical, virtual and service/application layer.

These are the layers (and not the OSI-architecture compliant layers) that the “cross layer” approach proposed in this paper refers to.

In this paper, we move a step forward from the work in the literature by providing a complete, and reliable architecture for monitoring and analyzing services based on metrics from all physical, virtual, and service layers. We propose an automated process of service profiling and network performance prediction which can assist the network operators to take a step forward in improving the utilization of their infrastructures without sacrificing QoS and/or service availability. This solution comes with two advantages: a) obviates the need to predefine a static profile for each service before its deployment, b) provides a continuous procedure for creating and updating the Machine Learning (ML) models based on data from the real deployment.

In the rest of the paper, we first examine relevant work in the field to provide a global view on the issue we tackle. In section III, we propose the novel mechanism/architecture along with indicative implementation options. Next, in section IV, we describe the sandbox environment that we deployed to validate the proposed mechanism and we discuss the obtained results focusing on the prediction accuracy. Finally, section V concludes the paper.

II. RELEVANT WORK

To address the aforementioned challenges, various approaches have been proposed in the literature [4] - [10]. Their main focus is on the context of NFV and especially on the deployment and validation of VNFs. A framework to designate the bottleneck on a VNF basis, under various system conditions has been proposed in [4] whilst the performance profiling is applied to an entire service chain, instead of isolated VNFs (as in [5], [6]) based on the rationale that even the position of a VNF within the service chain, may significantly impact the system performance. This is an important remark, as the profiling from a service chain perspective instead of an isolated VNF, can significantly increase the overall modeling accuracy. However, this approach does not take into account the importance of data from certain layers, e.g. the resource allocation on physical machines (PM), and thus the understanding of the actual effect of the physical resources on the QoS of each VNF cannot be identified. The importance of a unified representation of infrastructure has also been tackled in [7], [8] and has been implemented in [9], which however does not adopt ML. This deficiency is partially rectified in [10], where ML techniques to predict the needed resources for a specific Network Service (NS) are explored without however exploiting data from all three layers.

III. THE CROSS-LAYER MACHINE LEARNING-ASSISTED SOLUTION

A. System Architecture

To address the challenge for real time management and resource allocation in this dynamic environment, the SPs need to perform three discrete operations: a) impact analysis of the running services on the deployed infrastructure, with respect to resource usage and performance offered to the already running services, b) prediction of the resources required for each new service to be deployed for the required QoS and c) real-time allocation of the calculated resources. The proposed framework provides a useful starting point to the SPs, easy to be adapted to the concept of its own infrastructure with the development of ad hoc implementations of the three main components of the model (monitor, analyzer-predictor, actions activator).

The first operation aims to identify the system breaking points, which may cause potential instabilities or even service failures. This step is critical for the SP because based on this information, the SP can keep a safe distance from potential failures.

The second operation exploits the results from the previous one, in order to predict the amount of the required resources for any operational scenario. For this purpose, ML methods are employed spanning from empirical ones to more sophisticated approaches based on ML or Deep Learning [11].

Finally, the third operation aims to assign the estimated resources in real-time. Based on the predictions, the SP should proceed with the appropriate actions to allocate or free resources accordingly. Such actions can be the migration of a VM/container to another physical server, reconfiguration of the network slices, and scale in/out action of NS. It is obvious that these actions are performed by the management frameworks [12] that each SP uses, which is out of scope of this article.

The proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 1 and can be deployed in any datacenter, which provides virtual computational and network resources and in its typical form includes a) multiple hardware devices at the physical layer (equipment) layer, b) virtual resources (VMs, containers, SDN controllers) at the virtualization layer and c) application layer entities, which consist of the diverse services that run on this node. The proposed architecture consists of two main components (i) a cross-layer monitoring service and (ii) a data analysis service.

B. The new components / functionalities

The cross-layer data collection is realized by collecting data from the “monitoring probes” at each of the three layers and delivering them to the monitoring server. In more detail, regarding the application layer, the performance of each service can be easily measured by legacy monitoring solutions as many application servers, databases, etc. already provide monitoring tools to expose performance metrics. The information coming from the application layer is useful to define the break point of a service, but in most cases, the correlation of a specific failure with the actual cause is not straight forward.

The analysis service exploits the collected data to train various ML regression algorithms, spanning from linear regression to deep neural networks, which can accurately predict the performance under specific workload (affected by

the number of concurrent requests, packet size, etc.) and allocated resources (CPU, memory, network bandwidth, etc.). The overall accuracy depends on the adopted ML algorithm as well as on the dataset because, in principle, the accuracy improves with time, as the number of collected (and used for training) data is increasing while the service runs. The continuous training of the algorithms, (apart from improved accuracy) enables the system to profile any new service in the future. As a result, the impact of the workload parameters can be quantified for any possible resource configuration scenario.

The process of selecting the optimal ML algorithm could be as follows: the data that flow in are continuously compared with

Fig. 1. Proposed architecture which monitors and analyzes data from the application, virtualization and physical layer.

the predicted values. Once the prediction accuracy of the set of models has reached a threshold, a specific model per metric can be selected and used from this point on.

C. Technical considerations with business impact

During the design of the three-layer monitoring approach for data collection and analysis attention has been paid to *heterogeneity support, scalability, open-source technology adoption, modularity and deployment flexibility*. All these technical aspects have significant impact on the business exploitation potential of the approach as they affect the usability/applicability of the approach in different environments.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION IN REAL LIFE TEST BED

A. The sandbox test bed

To validate the proposed solution, we set up a sandbox environment in which we deployed the proposed architecture and a production set up of a quite common backend service consisting of a set of three micro-services: a) an HTTP Rest API server (Django rest framework), b) a relational database (Postgres), and c) a production web server (Nginx). The selection of the specific service type was based on the fact that backend implementations play a very critical role on the

performance of web services today and the application servers like Django are widely used in the industry. The physical infrastructure comprised two servers. In the first one, we installed all the components of the monitoring and analysis servers, and in the second one, we run VMware vSphere ESXi v7.0 which offered the VMs that hosted the under-test services. For the execution of the test, we used two VMs (2 vCPUs/8GRAM/storage 100GB each). Nginx and Django server were installed in the first VM (VM#3) and the database (DB) installed separately in the second VM (VM#4).

The components that were used in the proposed architecture are open-source Cloud Native implementations and more technical details of their configuration are available on [13].

1) *Monitoring Server*: The core component of the monitoring framework is Prometheus.io server, which stands as the central point of event monitoring, storage and alerting. All metrics from the three layers are collected, using an HTTP pull model, and stored in a timeseries database. Some of the key features that make this server suitable for the proposed architecture are: (a) use of a flexible query language (PromQL), which makes easier the interconnection with external systems (e.g. Analytics module); (b) existence of many open-source implementation (exporters) for exposing monitoring metrics from various applications, and it is also quite easy to create new ones; (c) autonomy as there is no reliance on complex distributed storage mechanisms; (d) the fact that new monitoring targets can be easily added via reconfiguration or using the file-based service discovery mechanisms.

Let us now turn our attention to the monitoring/probing mechanisms of the three layers. For the *physical layer monitoring*, (i.e., the monitoring of the physical servers), we chose Netdata.io, which is a powerful tool designed to collect a huge list of metrics from every system and application in real-time. For the *virtual machines monitoring* we used a Netdata plugin specially designed to collect metrics from vSphere ESXi. So, Prometheus collects the target metrics from the Netdata for both physical and virtual resources. Regarding the containers, we can easily integrate the appropriate tools (e.g. cAdvisor) or we can directly monitor Kubernetes cluster using Prometheus. For the application layer, to monitor the performance of the service under-test, we used two additional tools compatible with the monitoring server (Prometheus). The first one is an additional Django application that collects performance metrics from the server and exposes them to the Prometheus server. The second one is the Postgres exporter which also collects performance metrics from the DB and exposes them to the Prometheus.

2) *Machine Learning module*

We employed seven ML algorithms to find the relationship between the workload parameters and the target system metrics. These ML algorithms are: Multiple Linear Regression (LR), Multivariate Polynomial Regression (PR), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Regression (SVR), k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) and Deep Neural Network (DNN). They were selected from a long list of ML methods as the most suitable for our problem, as they provided high modeling accuracy along with very low computational times.

B. *The evaluation process*

The whole process comprises three phases: (1) stress testing phase, (2) profiling phase based on metrics collected via white - black box approach and (3) ML analysis phase. In the first phase, from the available open-source testbench implementations, we selected the Apache Bench, which fits better to the under-test service and we used it to transmit concurrent requests towards the examined service. During the second phase, a large number of metrics are collected from all three layers of the tested environment. The collection mechanism is based on both white and black box approaches. In the final phase, the number of recorded data are used to feed the ML algorithms which, after the proper training, provide predictions for each resource type. Due to lack of space, we present the result from the performance prediction phase.

We employed ML to dynamically predict the evolution of five performance metrics, namely CPU usage of two VMs and of the PM, network bandwidth and service time, under different operating conditions. For our validation, the number of measured data points used to feed the ML algorithms were 500 for each metric. These data points were attained by iterating over the following parameters:

Number of concurrent requests:

[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 15, 20]

Number of records in the DB (thousands):

[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100]

Record size (kB):

[0.18, 1, 3, 5, 7]

The 500 measured values were shuffled and divided in five datasets, where each dataset contained 300 values for training, 100 for validation and 100 for testing. Followingly, a circular rotation between training, validation and test sub-sets was performed to ensure that all 500 values will be tested. To obtain the optimal hyperparameter values for each examined metric, we used grid search for the seven ML algorithms. For example, for the prediction of the CPU usage and LR method, a 1st order polynomial hyperparameter was used while for PR, we used a 2nd order polynomial. The two nearest neighbors are adequate to provide the optimal accuracy when k-NN is employed, while a DNN with two hidden layers and eight neurons per layer is the optimal architecture for our problem. The depth of the DT is 6, 8 and 10, for the CPU usage, network bandwidth and service time, respectively, while the same depth was considered with 5, 20 and 10 estimators for the RF, for the three metric categories respectively. Finally, C and γ are the main hyperparameters of the SVR algorithm; in our cases, C takes the value of 50 while γ ranges between 0.005 and 0.03. It is worth mentioning that the value of each hyperparameter has a direct impact on the algorithmic complexity, e.g. a greater depth in DT and RF, results to a more extended algorithmic structure.

As an error metric, to attain comparable results among all examined metrics, the average absolute relative percentage error was used. The results are shown in Fig. 2. The Decision Trees and Random Forest outperform all other ML algorithms, as they can approximate functions with floors with great efficiency, (e.g. a floor in CPU usage is 100%). This is more evident in the most difficult-to-predict metric, which is the

Network Bandwidth, as it reaches a floor when the CPU usage reaches 100%, (i.e. after 10 concurrent requests, in our case).

Fig. 2. Comparison of seven ML algorithms applied to five system metrics.

Random Forest algorithm attains a maximum error of 6.7% in all five metrics, outperforming DT due to the use of multiple trees. Further, DNN exceeds 10% which can be attributed to the relatively small number of training samples (300 in each case). Next, PR is sufficient for four out of five cases, as the number of attributes is relatively small in our problem (three attributes), outperforming LR, as expected. K-NN and SVR show comparable performance as their error is less than 15% in four out of five cases.

The aforementioned analysis reveals that ML algorithms can predict the performance of critical system metrics with very good accuracy, less than 6.7% average error in our case, for a large number of different operational conditions, using only a small fraction of these conditions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a novel solution based on open-source tools that enables service providers to automatically profile network services, predict (using ML) the performance that these will experience for any resource allocation (deployment) scenario, which gives them the tools to identify “critical points” as well as the cause that is responsible for each failure. This information can be used for optimal resource allocation, higher resource utilization efficiency and guarantee certain level of QoS, which is important for the service providers. High prediction accuracy was observed (maximum error was less than 6.7% in all cases) validating the efficiency of our approach.

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